

INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPMENT AND WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP CHALLENGES IN INDIA

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Abstract:

Economic development of every nation is closely related to the advancement of women in each society. Women entrepreneurship has become an essential movement in many countries, including India. At governmental level, policies have been framed and initiatives are being taken for supporting and promoting women in setting up of business based on their interest and competency. But vast majority of women in India still face challenges in developing their business ideas and implementing them successfully in their own domain. This research paper is an exploration into the factors that motivate and challenge women in the process of enterprise development. A study of the socio economic condition of prospective women managers and entrepreneurs of a management school in India was conducted for this research to evaluate the attitude and decision making style of women based on their perceived challenges to initiate a start up business.

Key Words: *Industrial Development, Women Entrepreneurship, Decision Making, Women Empowerment*

Introduction:

Entrepreneurship is a multidimensional concept because its features vary according to the perspective of the viewer; let that be a sociologist, a banker or a management professional. Entrepreneurial activities are frequently assumed to involve risk-taking, especially relative to managerial activities within established corporations and hence men dominated the enterprise realm for ages. In the past, it was the deep seated approach of culture and gender difference between men and women that paved the way for establishment of men dominance in the entrepreneurial process. But now the scenario is changing. New generation women across the world have got over the old negative notions of being inferior to men in business field in terms of managerial decision, intellect and exposure.

India too has a pool of confident and determined women who are good entrepreneurs and who has great ideas to flag off great entrepreneurial ventures. But women are in minority as entrepreneurs in India despite the fact that female entrepreneurs are important source of economic growth in most developed and developing nations around the world. There are a number of factors that influence the decision making of women to be entrepreneurs and this study focuses on Indian women's exposure to market/industry, challenges in fund raising for their business activities, the factors influencing their decision making and risk taking ability, knowledge about governments entrepreneurial development programs and the role of support networks and schemes which in turn determines successful entry to market and maintenance of business operations.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The study was planned with the following objectives:

1. To understand the role of women entrepreneurs in industrial development of India.
2. To identify the major constraints faced by prospective women entrepreneurs.
3. To propose suggestions for effective women enterprise development mechanism.

NEED OF STUDY

Women are capable of becoming the key agents of sustainable development in every economy. But very rarely female of the population come forward with their entrepreneurial plans and establish new pattern and process of development in business field. The role and initiative of women in stepping up as entrepreneurs are pivotal for social transformation. This study explores how women entrepreneurs can be empowered so as to contribute towards industrial development in India. There are a plethora of research works on the factors that drives women to take up entrepreneurship, the challenges that women entrepreneurs face in Indian market due to social and work cultures, the dependency of women on family and peers for their career decision making etc. But there are very few studies on how women can be empowered to establish a sound business start up with success strategies. Hence this research paper proposes a triple support system for women entrepreneurial development in India.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The study is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data is collected from women who intend to be entrepreneurs in future, currently pursuing Masters Degree in Business Management. The sample size is 90 and the

sample was selected using non random opportunity sampling technique. The analysis of data was done using Weighted Ranking Method so as to identify the main challenges faced by women while they plan to start up a business in India.

REVIEW OF LITERATURES

Industrial Development and Entrepreneurship: The term Entrepreneur originates from the French word 'Entreprendre' which means 'to undertake'. Entrepreneurs identify opportunities, assemble required resources, implement a practical action plan, and harvest the reward in a timely, flexible way (Sahlman and Stevenson 1991, p. 1). Peter Drucker (2012) in his book "Innovation and Entrepreneurship" identifies entrepreneurs as the those who always search for changes, responds to it, and exploits it as an opportunity. Drucker has also observed that fast changing markets have an effect on the decision making process in organizations. Hence there is an inference that industrial development and entrepreneurship are in direct correlation with decision making of skill and process of by entrepreneurs and executive managers.

Women Entrepreneurship in India: The Government of India has defined women entrepreneurs as 'a enterprise owned and controlled by women having a minimum financial interest of 51 per cent of the capital and giving at least 51 per cent of the employment generated in the enterprise to women'. The micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSME) sector played a significant role in this through innovation, diversification, and employment generation. In India, around 3.01 million women-owned enterprises represent about 10 percent of all MSMEs in the country. Collectively, they contribute only about 3.09 percent of industrial output. Approximately 78 percent of women enterprises belong to the services sector. Women entrepreneurship is largely skewed towards smaller sized firms, as almost 98 percent of women-owned businesses are micro-enterprises and nearly 90 percent of women-owned enterprises are in the informal sector.

Despite changes in political, social, economic and cultural settings, the India Labour and Employment Report (ILER) 2014_prepared by Institute for Human Development (IHD) and the Indian Society of Labour Economics shows that there is a noteworthy trend of decline in the work participation of females in India during the period 2005-12. In spite of the increase in the female enrolment in higher education in India is high when compared to earlier decades the percentage of women involved in entrepreneurial jobs is still considerably undersized. The employment of women remains 20 to 40 per cent below that of men. 48percent of Indian population are women. But their participation in industrial development of India is nominal. Looking into statistics, the total number of female employees in the SSI sector in India is estimated at 33,17,496 during the financial year 2013-14. About 57.62 percent of the female employees were employed in the Small Scale Industry (SSI) units located in the States of Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Karnataka, West Bengal and Andhra Pradesh. (SSI India census, 2015) But when it comes to women entrepreneurs, it constitutes only 7.36percent (26.61 Lakhs) of Indian entrepreneurs according to MSME 2014 Annual Report, p.25. The lowest female ownership rates are in Rajasthan, Bihar, Orissa, and Uttar Pradesh, each with 6 percent or less.

Drivers and Challenges in Women Entrepreneurship:

Most women take up entrepreneurial opportunity in their quest for being more expressive, authoritative and independent Cohoon, Wadhwa & Mitchell (2010) made an exploration on motivational factors that drive men and women to entrepreneurship. The findings of the study shows that 59% of successful women entrepreneurs had founded two or more companies and the top five financial and psychological factors motivating women to become entrepreneurs are desire to build the wealth, the wish to capitalize own business ideas they had, the appeal of startup

culture, a long standing desire to own their own company and working with someone else did not appeal them. According to this study, the challenges are more related with entrepreneurship rather than gender.

In the study conducted by Vijayakumar and Naresh (2013) the factors that influence women to be entrepreneurs are their high level of confidence, risk taking ability, urge for economic independence and to establish self identity, self motivation, and requirement of equal status in society, creative ideas, freedom, mobility and achievement of excellence. Earlier Moore and Buttner (1997) identified that self determination, expectation for recognition, self esteem and career goal are the key drivers for taking up entrepreneurship by women. There are also studies that states that dismal economic conditions, unemployment in family and need for self dependency compels women to entrepreneurship activities in some cases.

According to Bharadwaj et al (2012), the major hurdles that the women face during starting and running a company generally come from financing and balancing of life. The balancing of life is caused due to lack of family support for the women. The other hindering external factors include gender discrimination, inaccessibility to information, training opportunities, infrastructure etc. Some internal factors like risk aversion by women, lack of confidence, lack of vision of strategic leader etc. can also create obstacles for the women entrepreneurship development.

Gender Disparity: Human Development Report (HDR) released by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) in Tokyo has ranked India 135 in HDI from among 187 countries and the ratio of female to male HDI in India is reported as 0.828 (Economic Times, 2014). Human Development Index (HDI) is a composite index measuring average achievement in three basic dimensions of human development—a long and healthy life, knowledge and a decent standard of living. According to the study conducted by Hausmann, Tyson and Zahidi (2011), India's score for women participation and opportunity is worse than 95percent of all countries in a sample of above 120 countries.

Despite recent economic advances, India's gender balance for entrepreneurship remains among the lowest in the world. Improving this balance is an important step for India's development and its achievement of greater economic growth and gender equality" (Ghani, 2014). The 2014 World Economic Forum's Gender Gap Index (GGI) ranked India 114 out of 142 countries on economic participation and opportunity, educational attainment, health and survival. GGI assesses how well countries are dividing their resources and opportunities among their male and female populations, regardless of the overall levels of these resources and opportunities.

In 2014 Human Development Report Office (HDRO) introduced a gender development index (GDI) for the first time, which measures gender development gaps among 148 countries. From the report it can be seen that the per capita income for men in India is triple that for women. Estimated Gross national income (GNI) per capita for women in India is 2277 and that of men is 7833 based on ILO report (2013), United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UN DESA) (2013) and World Bank (2014) Reports. The numbers have been derived on the basis of the ratio of female to male wage, female and male shares of economically active population, and GNI.

Funding: When it comes to need of finance and accessibility to funds, women in India face more ceilings, than elsewhere. Although the financing needs for women-owned enterprises are not radically different from the needs of male-owned enterprises, the level of financial exclusion is higher due to a combination of factors. When the limited financial awareness and understanding of financial products/ services and lack of adequate collateral coupled with lack of confidence or hesitation to approach financial institutions stands in the demand side of constraints to get finance, the perception of higher risk profile for women in the absence of collateral security and guarantee or support by male family member serves as impediment in the supply side of access to finance. Also, the social status

of women and prevalent social norms in India influence perceptions of financial institutions and the ability of women entrepreneurs to access finance. The key demand and supply side constraints specific to women (IFC, 2014)

Networking: Porter (2000) pointed out, ‘local proximity is essential for accessing these knowledge spill overs. This makes the value of an entrepreneurial firm greater in the (local) presence of other entrepreneurial firms. The value of any individuals or firms capabilities is therefore conditional upon the existence of partners in a network’. According to David Audretsch (2003) ‘Network externalities result from the value of an individual’s or firm’s capabilities being conditional upon the geographic proximity of complementary firms and individuals’.

Research has shown that women entrepreneurs of industries like engineering, pharmaceuticals and information technology are more inclusive and collaborative in their decision making. A study among 600 board directors found that women attend more to relationships and takes up challenges of balancing multiple stakeholders interest. The cooperative approach to decision making among women entrepreneurs helps in building up better and productive collaborations and consensus. This virtue has proved to be helpful for established and successful women entrepreneurs in western countries. But according to studies, this inclusiveness and collaborations have turned out to be over dependency of women on their partner, family and peers which is a vice for start up women entrepreneurs in India.

Another study among successful business entrepreneurs outside India has revealed that women seek advice and guidance from a greater range of advisors, bankers, accountants, consultants, media persons, other business owners and family before decision making and this serves as either a direct or an indirect support mechanism for their entrepreneurial development. This attribute is not by itself a nature of women but in fact it is something nurtured by woman who are proactive, focused and goal oriented.

Infrastructure: According to a study conducted by Ghani, Kerr and O’Connell (2013) on Promoting Women’s Economic Participation in India, the huge disparities in women’s economic participation in India is the result of poor infrastructure, gender composition in labour force, deficiency in social and business networks and low share of incumbent female entrepreneurs. It was observed in their study that there is a direct nexus between policies of government on infrastructure development and entry of female in entrepreneurship. Inadequacy of infrastructure affects women more than men for reasons associated to safety concerns and social norms in India. The report states that female connections in labour markets and local buyer/seller (input-output) markets contribute to a higher entry share. Study recommends that empowerment of women can be achieved through increase in their participation in labour force, reduction in discrimination and wage differentials, introduction of practices to promote talented women into leadership and managerial roles, etc.

Government Schemes and Projects for Women Entrepreneurs: Legislatives have identified that improvement of women’s social and economic status is essential for achievement of the goal of women empowerment in India. Hence women empowerment initiatives of Indian government have been crafted to make the female population economically more independent and self reliant. With this objective as core, many schemes and policies were framed by Indian government to promote women entrepreneurs in terms of their skill development, funding for business and expand their business activities through networking. The Industrial policy of 1991 envisaged a special entrepreneurial training program in India to support women entrepreneurs. Indian government has implemented schemes to ensure the empowerment and development of women at various levels starting off from Integrated Rural Development Programme (IRDP), Training of Rural Youth for Self-Employment (TRYSEM) Prime Minister’s, Rojgar Yojana (PMRY), Women’s Development Corporations (WDCs) Marketing of Non-Farm Products of Rural Women (MAHIMA), Assistance to Rural Women in Non-Farm Development (ARWIND) schemes, Trade Related Entrepreneurship Assistance and Development (TREAD), Working Women’s Forum, Indira Mahila Yojana, Indira Mahila Kendra, Mahila Samiti Yojana, Mahila Vikas Nidhi, Micro Credit Scheme, Micro & Small Enterprises Cluster Development Programmes (MSE-CDP), Rajiv Gandhi Mahila Vikas Pariyojana (RGMVP), Priyadarshini

Project and so on (Vijayakumar and Naresh, 2013). Among these programs, self employment and credit schemes offered by government are the predominant ones. But very few women in India are aware of such programs and among those who are aware, there are many, who have not availed the benefits of the system due to their lack of their decision making skill.

Institutional Support: There are a good number of institutions in India that are aided by government and NGO's working for the upliftment of women interested in self employment and entrepreneurship. World Development Report had highlighted that empowering half of the potential workforce has significant economic benefits beyond promoting just gender equality (World Bank 2012). Considering the significance of this observation, various Entrepreneurs Development Programs (EDP's) are being organised by different institutions at state and central levels to promote entrepreneurial activities in India.

Most organisations conduct training programs on regular basis for women enterprise development, offer support and guidance for business development and business networking. Few well known organisations that work towards empowerment of business women in India are Federation of Indian Women Entrepreneurs (FIWE), Consortium of Women Entrepreneurs(CWEI), Self-Employed Women's Association (SEWA), Women Entrepreneurs Promotion Association (WEPA), The Marketing Organisation of Women Enterprises (MOOWES), Chamber Women Entrepreneurship Council Women Entrepreneurs , Tie Stree Shakti (TSS) and Women Empowerment Corporation.

LIMITATION OF RESEARCH

Primary research was limited to perception of 90 management students in an autonomous business school in India. The down side of opportunity sampling used in the research is that the opinion shared by participants might not be the reflection of representative perception of all future women entrepreneurs or female management student, due to environmental, cultural or socio economic factors that dominate the Kerala market conditions.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Profile: The participants of the study fall within an age group of 20 and 28, all female, majority unmarried, hailing mainly from south of Kerala and doing Masters in Business Administration after graduation in various streams like Commerce (60%), Science (12%), Arts and other (28%), in a reputed Business school in Kerala, India.

Drivers: The main factors that motivate women to become an entrepreneur, according to the study, are their passion to independent, creative and productive. The stories of role models in the field also inspire them to take initiatives for enterprise development. Financial independence and lifestyle of successful entrepreneurs was rated low in motivation level, but women expressed their inclination for recognition and power that accompanies success in entrepreneurship.

Challenges: The survey questionnaire comprised of questions pertaining to challenging factors for women in Enterprise Development. The data was collected to evaluate the perception of prospective management professional and the findings of the research are presented hereunder:

Sl. No	Weight	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Rank
	Particulars	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X		
1.	Lack of Confidence	4	12	13	5	12	5	9	16	9	5	491	6
		40	108	104	35	72	25	36	48	18	5		
2.	Financial Deficit	20	8	2	15	5	12	10	8	4	6	561	2
		200	72	16	105	30	60	40	24	8	6		
3.	Lack of Information	10	8	8	4	20	10	10	6	4	10	478	7
		100	72	64	36	100	40	30	18	8	10		
4.	Lack of Institutional Support	13	5	9	10	11	5	9	9	9	10	499	4
		130	45	72	70	66	25	36	27	18	10		
5.	Family Pressures	8	11	8	3	5	9	10	13	11	12	452	9
		80	99	64	21	30	45	40	39	22	12		
6.	Lack of Training	3	7	11	4	8	12	10	13	10	12	426	10
		30	63	88	28	46	60	40	39	20	12		
7.	Lack of Infrastructure	4	13	12	8	9	5	10	12	12	5	493	5
		40	117	96	56	54	25	40	36	24	5		
8.	Gender Inequality	5	10	11	12	10	10	8	9	9	6	505	3
		50	90	88	84	60	50	32	27	18	6		
9.	Lack of Mentors	8	10	9	15	14	12	12	5	3	2	562	1
		80	90	72	105	84	60	48	15	6	2		
10.	Other Problems	10	9	8	3	10	3	12	9	16	10	462	8
		100	81	64	21	60	15	48	27	36	10		

On the basis of above data, it may be concluded that finding the right mentor who can advice and support women in enterprise development is a major challenge for women while developing their business ideas. This can be attributed to their lack of networking skills and exposure to professional business circle. Limited access to mentors and exclusion from elite networks deem to stop women from exploring existing and future entrepreneurial support programs for business development in India.

Many women give up their business plans due to non availability of adequate funds. Most women are unaware of the changing modes of fund raising. The concept of raising funds through Angel investors, Venture capitalists, Micro funding facilities and Crowd funding etc are still new to many participants of survey despite being students of business management. Thirdly the survey reveals that women in India still face and fear gender inequality in their way to professional development and it evidently stands in the way to self dependency and self expression.

Lack of institutional support in providing incubation facilities, has been highlighted by many women who participated in the study. But it is mainly because of their unawareness of the availability of programs and schemes introduced by state and central government at various levels. The presence of various NGO's and their support roles are not known to many, leading to wastage of one's own potential for growth and development in profession.

Lack of Infrastructure is yet another factor that poses threat to women entrepreneurs as already funding by itself is a challenge in their enterprise development. Government need to provide more infrastructural facilities exclusive for women to make good the situation. All other challenging factors considered in the study where linked to these five key factors and hence need to be read together for clarity of concept.

From secondary data analysis it can be inferred that despite growth and progress in Indian political and economic system, women entrepreneurship remain an untapped source of nation's wealth. With only about 13 per cent of enterprises in the registered micro, small and medium enterprises sector being managed by women, women's entrepreneurship is an important human resource for industrial growth in India. Again the position of India in Gender Gap Index and Gender Development Index indicates the collective socio cultural mindset that is prevailing in the country towards women.

RECOMMENDATION

Women should be the principle force behind nation's future economy. In spite of being the second fastest growing economy in the world, gender disparity is tooted deep and persistent in India. Steps need to tackle the situation. Increase in access to business capital, including micro finances, venture capital funds and crowd funding will help women entrepreneurs to grow substantially. There is a transformation happening at global and national level in terms of women empowerment. Decision making styles of entrepreneurs are changing. Business models are changing. Women entrepreneurs in India should come forward to lead this transformation phase through examples. For the purpose of facilitating this vision, the researcher herein recommends a three tier support system for women entrepreneurship program for Industrial development in India.

Figure: Three Tire Support System

Governmental Support: Governmental intervention in women entrepreneurship should go beyond policy formulations. Indian Prime Minister, Narendra Modi has a vision of ‘Make in India’ which has created new opportunities for business and it has also created a capital surplus which can fuel entrepreneurship in urban and rural parts of India. Micro enterprise development is a feasible way for economic development of nation and addresses issue to difficulty in attaining financial aid from lenders and financiers. Allocation of an Industrial Estate for Women Entrepreneurs and formation of Women Entrepreneurs Guidance Cell are all in cards. But expressly raising demand for assistance is required to initiate the process and proceedings. Making a futuristic business plan with a SMART vision and objective is essential for standing apart and making entrepreneurial venture a success.

Institutional Support: Business incubators at technical and management schools are the best initiatives that would provide an undisruptive environment for young women entrepreneurs to work on their ideas. Hence women empowerment through entrepreneurship development programs at educational institutions and at community levels can be one best strategy of industrial development in India in the years to come. Launching of incubators and entrepreneurial cells that offer technical knowledge and micro financing assistance along with entrepreneurial skills training at all women poly technical colleges, arts and management schools, can help women to get over hurdles of lack of support and initiative. If the ideas are inventive and creative in nature, institution can by itself or through association with governmental or non governmental agencies offer financial support to the deserving aspirants.

Individual / Self Support: Every business initiative is a gamble and success of every initiate is depended on a number of factors. Self determination to establish and flourish in the market is as important as self confidence to take the risk and deal with success and failure. Having a thorough understanding of the market and its mobility along with volatility helps women entrepreneurs to work towards opportunities and face the challenges as efficiently as the other gender. It is the knowledge and preparedness that gives the cutting edge in dealing with contingencies of business.

Conclusion

Entrepreneurs shape the society, by taking chances. They grab the foreseeable opportunity that exist in the market and creates new wealth and job opportunities. Entrepreneurship is not just starting a new business or reviving an existing business. It is the realisation of a dream and an attitude for being creative and innovative and hence adding values to society. Women entrepreneurs should be brought to light through media exposures, support of peer groups, business networking and with more participation in policy implementation process. Women need to be self empowered to realise her own potentials and be willing to take chances when they have a passion for business. Considering the fears and challenges experienced by women, family and society need to drive them towards risk taking and decision making. Educational institutions should provide opportunities for self expression and extend all possible institutional assistance to trigger women enterprise development in each state of India.

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